

DE-CONSTRUCTING INHERITANCE RIGHTS OF WOMEN UNDER SANTHAL CUSTOMARY LAWS VIS-A-VIS HINDU SUCCESSION ACT, 1956

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Abstract

The laws dealing with intestate and testamentary succession in India are not uniform. A variety of laws are in vogue whose application depends on multiple factors. While the Hindus, Muslims, Christians, Parsis and the Jews have distinct personal laws of their own, the Scheduled Tribes in India are governed by their uncodified customary laws of inheritance and enjoy constitutional protection of their culture and identity. Customary laws of tribals are majorly left untouched based on the assumption that it is in the best interests of the concerned tribal communities. The same, however, need not be necessarily true. Further, women empowerment and gender justice is a common phenomenon of modern democratic world which is receiving a high degree of popularity in all the societies but nevertheless, it must be implemented keeping in view social concerns and with the help and support of each and every component of society. A woman can be said to be truly empowered when she is economically so and this depends, inter alia, on their right to hold and inherit property.

Keywords: *Santhal, Customary law, Hindu Succession Act, 1956.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Empowering women is a prerequisite for creating a good nation, when women are empowered, society with stability is assured. Empowerment of women is essential as their thoughts and their value systems lead to the development of a good family, good society and ultimately a good nation.

-A.P.J. Abdul Kalam

The laws dealing with intestate² and testamentary succession³ in India are not uniform. A variety of different laws are in vogue and their application

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² The term 'intestate succession' is used to denote the laws relating to inheritance. The property of a person, on his or her death, in absence of instructions left by him or her with respect to its devolution, devolves in accordance with the law of intestate succession to which the deceased was subject at the time of his or her death.

³ The term 'testamentary succession' refers to devolution of property through a testament or a will. A will that is capable of taking effect in law governs succession to the property of a person after his or her death in accordance with the rules laid down in the laws governing testamentary succession to the property of a person to which he or she was subject at the

depends on multiple factors. Personal laws in India owe their diversity to their varied origin, distinct principles and the bulk of substantive law itself. Broadly speaking, people adhering to five different religions live in India, viz. the Hindus, Muslims, Christians, Parsis and the Jews who have distinct laws. Besides, the Scheduled Tribes in India are governed by their uncodified customary laws of inheritance and enjoy constitutional protection of their culture and identity.

The present paper is an endeavour taken up by the researcher to make an analytical study of the inheritance rights of women under the Santhal customary laws vis-à-vis the Hindu Succession Act, 1956 and to analyze the possibility of the application of the Hindu Succession Act, 1956 on the Santhals professing the Hindu religion.

The researcher has divided the paper into six parts which are followed by a testing of the hypothesis and conclusion based on the research done. Part I contains an introduction to the entire paper followed by a detailed study of inheritance rights of women under the Santhal customary laws in Part II. The study has been classified under three heads: unmarried, married and widow wherein the rights available to each are discussed. Part III comprises of a comprehensive study of the provisions of the Hindu Succession Act, 1956 which bestow inheritance rights upon women. In Part IV, a comparative study of inheritance rights available to women under the Hindu Succession Act, 1956 and Santhal customary laws has been made. The researcher has further divided it into several sub topics to present the said comparisons cohesively. In Part V, the researcher has made a humble attempt to explore the scope of applicability of the Hindu Succession Act, 1956 to Santhals professing the Hindu religion. The researcher has concluded the paper in the last part wherein she has tested the hypothesis and given concluding observations with regard to the subject-matter of this paper.

II. INHERITANCE RIGHTS OF WOMEN UNDER SANTHAL CUSTOMARY LAWS

Santhals, one of the largest tribes of India are spread over West Bengal, Orissa, Bihar, Jharkhand and parts of Assam and Tripura. Inheritance rules are complex among the Santhals. Inheritance involves transfer of property from one generation or individual to another.⁴ The Santhals are patriarchal

time of his or her death. Diversity prevails in the laws of testamentary succession also, yet it is not as varied as in case of laws of inheritance or intestate succession.

⁴National Commission for Women, *Tribal Customary Law and Women's Status in North East India* (2005), available at <http://ncw.nic.in/pdfreports/Customary%20Law.pdf> (Last visited on July 26, 2013).

and patrilineal people. The succession is ordinarily in favour of the son, but in their absence it is in favour of the daughter, and in their absence in favour of the relative.⁵ There is some inheritance of movable property like clothes, ornaments utensils, and livestock which women carry along with them on marriage but women cannot inherit land, because they marry out of the clan.⁶ In default of sons, the closest collateral agnate or a live-at-home son-in-law (the *ghar-jawae*) inherits. In short, Santhal customary law provides for the inheritance of property in male line; in exceptional cases it can also be inherited by females, albeit temporarily.⁷

Although there is no codified law on inheritance rights of Santhali women, the same can be deduced from the *Final Report on the Revision Survey and Settlement Operations in the district of Sonthal Parganas, 1922-35* prepared by J.F. Gantzer wherein he has stated the Santhal Tribal Law of Inheritance as follows:⁸

As per the Santhal tribal laws it is only males who can inherit land. The general rule is that sons succeed their father jointly. If brothers are co-sharers in a holding and one brother dies without issue, the other surviving brothers and the sons of the other predeceased brothers inherit his share per stripes. The Santhal tribal law is quite definite and strict in not allowing females to inherit, but as per tribal customs, it is permissible for a man with no sons and only daughters to take a son-in-law into his house as a *Gharjamai* and to give him all the rights of a son thereby. The adoption of a *Gharjamai* is a formal proceeding resulting in the *Gharjamai* cutting off all connection with his own family as far as his rights to property are concerned, and becoming for all intents and purposes the son of his father-in-law. After such adoption has been formally completed, the *Gharjamai* can succeed as a son and oust other male relatives. However, it must be noted that a *Gharjamai* can be adopted only by a deliberate public act in the presence of the village community at the time of the marriage, and at a later stage, a father-in-law cannot convert an ordinary son-in-law into a

⁵ Jigyansu Tribal Research Centre, *Report on Codification of Customary Laws and Inheritance Laws in the Tribal Societies of Orissa* (1993) at 30, available at <http://www.indiankanoon.org/doc/450953/?type=print> (Last visited on July 23, 2013).

⁶ Nitya Rao, *Good Women do not inherit Land: Politics of Land and Gender in India* 203, Social Science Press (2008).

⁷ Ramesh Chandra, *Contextual Need for Change in Santhal Customary Law of Inheritance in Tribes in India –Ongoing Challenges* 345, MD Publications (R.S. Mann ed., 1996).

⁸ J.F. Gantzer, *Final Report on the Revision Survey and Settlement Operations in the district of Sonthal Parganas, 1922-35* (1936), cited in *Narayan Soren &ors. v. Ranjan Murmu &ors.*, Appellate Decree No. 292 of 1987(P), December 12, 2008 (M. Y. Eqbal J.), (Jharkhand High Court), available at <http://indiankanoon.org/doc/890826/> (Last visited on July 26, 2013).

Gharjamai. A widow also cannot create a *Gharjamai* under any circumstances.

With regard to widows, he has not made many entries but from whatever entries have been made it is evident that just like in the case of Hindu widow, a Santhal widow also inherits the property from her late husband and on her death, it will revert to those male relations who would ordinarily have inherited it at once under Santhal Law.

In the *Final Report on the Survey and Settlement Operations in the district of Sonthal Parganas, 1898-1907*, H. McPherson sets forth Santhal customary law on the subject of inheritance which was followed in disputes involving inheritance that arose during the settlement in Santhal villages as follows:⁹

If a woman dies while her sons are unmarried, they cannot demand a share in her property even if their father takes a second wife, but they can do so if they like after they get married. The father and the sons get one share each. On the death of the father and in the event of the second wife being childless, the sons of the first wife can take the share their father got, subject to the condition that they will have to pay for the funeral of their step-mother.

If a woman is left a widow without sons, her husband's father or his brothers inherit the whole property. The woman gets only a calf, one bandi of paddy, one bati and one cloth, and has to return to her parents' house. Some men keep their elder brother's widow and do not let her return to her parents' house, which is considered very praiseworthy. However, the brother who keeps the widow will get only his own share out of his deceased brother's property; he will not take the whole.

If a widow has no son and has only daughters, their paternal grandfather and uncles will take care of the widow and her daughters, and the property shall also remain in their possession. On coming of age, they will marry off the daughters and they will also give the daughters whatever presents their father would have given them at their marriage. After the marriage of all the daughters, the widow will get the perquisites of a childless widow and go to live in her father's house or she will go and live with her daughters.

⁹H. McPherson, *Final Report on the Survey and Settlement Operations in the District of Santhal Parganas, 1898-1907* (1909), cited in *Narayan Soren &ors. v. Ranjan Murmu &ors.*, Appellate Decree No. 292 of 1987(P), December 12, 2008 (M. Y. Eqbal J.), (Jharkhand High Court), available at <http://indiankanoon.org/doc/890826/> (Last visited on July 26, 2013).

The widow with a son gets to keep all the property in her own possession; the grandfather and uncles can only supervise to see that the widow does not waste the property. If a widow gets remarried before her sons are married, the grandfather and uncles will take over the possession of the property and she will cease to have any right in the property. Sometimes a calf is given her out of kindness and is called *bhandkar*.¹⁰

In the light of the work of the above mentioned scholars with regard to the inheritance rights of Santhal women, the rules of inheritance have been comprehensively enumerated hereafter:

A. UNMARRIED DAUGHTER

The unmarried daughter ordinarily has no right at all in the land. Land is usually equally divided among the brothers, with certain small portions going to daughters as dowry. She cannot ask for partition as a matter of right and in the event of her brothers separating, some land may be kept by her father or brothers for financing her marriage and maintaining her. It must be noted that that is done only to fulfill their duties towards her and does not confer upon her any rights as such. On partition of her father's property, she has no right to any share in it and only has a right to maintenance. She can acquire land of her own which is her absolute property. In certain cases, unmarried girls may inherit land, but the land reverts to her brothers when she gets married. If her father or her brothers or her father's agnates are unwilling to discharge their duties, she can claim enough land for her sustenance till she gets married. If her father dies without leaving behind other heirs or agnates, she will inherit his land and hold it until she gets married. If she is married, her other married sisters (if any) will share equally with her and if she does not have any sisters, the property goes to the village community.¹¹

B. MARRIED DAUGHTER

Married daughters are given two to three bighas of land situated in her parental village at the time of marriage, which is called *Taben Jom* (sufficient to eat) or maintenance. In respect of that property, right of the father, brothers or agnates are extinguished. Such property is her absolute property. On her death her son(s) inherit her property and in their absence, it passes on to her father, brother, or other male agnates but not to her husband.¹²

¹⁰Chaturbhuj Sahu, *The Santhal Women: A Social Profile* 76, South Asia Books (1996).

¹¹ Rao, *supra* note 4, at 204.

¹²*Ibid.*

If a married daughter has no brother, her father may adopt her husband and take him to his house as a live-at-home son-in-law (*Gharjamai*) and to give him thereby all the rights of a son.

C. WIDOW

With regard to the right of the widow, her status is that of a Hindu widow¹³ having right to maintenance only. If her husband expired while he was a joint holder with his brothers, she continues to live in the family and her situation does not differ materially from what it was in her husband's lifetime. Her right to maintenance continues and if her husband's family neglects her without cause, she can demand sufficient land for her sustenance. In the event of a complete family partition, the widow and her children will get the share which her deceased husband would have got if had he been alive. The widow gets life estate like Hindu widow's estate¹⁴.

If a woman is left a widow without sons, her husband's father or his brothers will inherit the entire property. She will get only a calf, one bandi of paddy, one bati and one cloth, and will have to return to her parents' house. There are some men who let their elder brother's widow stay in her deceased husband's house and do not let her go back to her parents' place. This act is considered very praiseworthy. However, the brother who keeps the widow will get only his own share of the deceased brother's property; he will not take the whole.

If a widow has daughters, their paternal grandfather and uncles will take charge of mother and daughters, and the property shall remain in their possession as well. When the daughters come of age, they will marry off the daughters and they will also give the daughters whatever presents their father would have given them at their marriage. After the marriage of all the daughters, the widow will be given the perquisites of a childless widow and will have to live in either her father's house or with her daughters.

The widow with a son gets to keep all the property in her own possession; the grandfather and uncles can only watch over to see that the wife does not

¹³Her status is that of a Hindu widow as it was before the coming into force of the Hindu Succession Act, 1956. A female Hindu inherits from male as well as female relatives including brothers, or allotted to her on partition. Accumulations of the income and accretions made to the estate may be added to this. The Hindu woman had only a limited interest in the property and her interest is known as 'Hindu Woman's Estate' or 'widow's estate'. She is merely entitled to the enjoyment of the property without any power of disposal over it. She is entitled to its beneficial enjoyment as long as she is alive to the exclusion of all others and is answerable to none unless she is guilty of wrongful waste. Nobody is entitled to deprive her of it or to deal with the property in any manner detrimental to her.

¹⁴Sarad Chandra Roy, *The Origins of Chotanagpur* 369- 370 (1915).

waste the property. If a widow remarries before her sons get married, their paternal grandfather and uncles take possession over the property and she ceases to have any right to get anything. At times, she is given a calf out of kindness which is called *bhandkar*.¹⁵

III. HINDU WOMEN'S INHERITANCE RIGHTS UNDER THE HINDU SUCCESSION ACT, 1956

With respect to the property rights of a Hindu woman, the dictates of ancient texts were multifarious; some recommending the granting of share to her and some restricting her from acquiring it herself or hold it as an absolute owner. Customary practices similarly denied her absolute ownership and restricted her rights to maintenance. Judiciary decisions gave her some relief but they could not lay down a general rule as they were confined to specific cases. Legislative steps were taken to improve her position and in terms of her ability to acquire property, Hindu women have come a long way to the present day.

A. RIGHT OF WOMEN OVER PROPERTY UNDER SECTION 6

By virtue of the amendment to Section 6¹⁶, a daughter of a coparcener in a Hindu joint family governed by the Mitakshara law becomes a coparcener in her own right from her birth and thus enjoys rights equal to those enjoyed by a son of a coparcener. She is invested with all the rights including the right to seek partition of the coparcenary property and to become Karta of the joint Hindu family. A proviso has been added to Section 6(1) providing that any dispositions or alienations, including a partition or testamentary disposition, entered into before 20 December, 2004 are not affected, with the object of making the provision prospective.

Section 6(2) stipulates that any property to which a female Hindu becomes entitled under Section 6(1) would be held by her with all the incidents of coparcenary ownership. Notwithstanding anything contained in the Act or any other law, such property could be disposed of by such female by testamentary disposition. The section is limited to coparcenary property and does not extend to 'any property'.

Though Section 6 has been substituted by emphasizing the right of a daughter as a coparcener, Section 6(2) stipulates the right of any female Hindu over coparcenary property. The wife of a deceased coparcener is also entitled to a share as his widow. In *Gurupad v Hirabai*, the Supreme Court

¹⁵Sahu, *supra* note 9, at 76.

¹⁶Section 6, The Hindu Succession Act, 1956.

held that a widow is entitled to an equal share as that of her sons and daughters in the coparcenary property.¹⁷

B. LIMITED OWNERSHIP CONVERTED INTO FULL OWNERSHIP

Section 14 of the present Act, converted the limited ownership into full-fledged ownership and also ended the confusion and controversy regarding the exact share that the widow took on the death of her husband as an undivided member in the Mitakshara coparcenary. Presently, she inherits the separate property of her husband as his primary heir, and the quantum of her share and the nature of her estate are absolutely identical to that of the son. From the undivided share of the deceased husband in the Mitakshara coparcenary, her presence defeats the application of the doctrine of survivorship over his undivided share and prevents it from going to the surviving coparceners. The share of the deceased husband is ascertained by means of a notional partition and she inherits his share as his class-I heir, taking it as an absolute owner.

For widows who, on the date of the passing of the Act, were in possession of the property as limited owners, it was provided that henceforth, they would hold these as full owners thereof.

Section 14 provides:¹⁸

Property of a female Hindu to be her absolute property.- Any property possessed by a female Hindu, whether acquired before or after the commencement of this Act, shall be held by her as full owner thereof and not as a limited owner.

Explanation: In this sub-section, 'Property' includes both movable and immovable property acquired by a female Hindu by inheritance or devise, or at a partition or in lieu of maintenance or arrears of maintenance or by gift from any person, whether a relative or not, before, at or after her marriage, or by her own skill or exertion, or by purchase or by prescription or in any other manner whatsoever and also any such property held by her as *stridhana* immediately before the commencement of this Act.

As full owner and not as a limited owner

The expression 'full owner' has been used in the sense of absolute ownership and in contradiction to the term 'limited owner' which had received special significance under the old law. The expression 'full

¹⁷ S. A. Desai, Mulla: Principles of Hindu Law Vol. II 324, Lexis Nexis Butterworths (2007).

¹⁸Section 14, The Hindu Succession Act, 1956.

ownership' is used in this section in the context of property and denotes a right indefinite with regard to user, unrestricted with regard to disposition, unlimited with regard to duration and heritable as such right by the heirs of the owner. These words show that in the circumstances mentioned in Section 14(1), the limited interest held by the female Hindu will be held by her as full owner, on and from the date of commencement of the Act. It is the limited interest that is transformed into an absolute interest.

Property acquired before the Act

In respect of the property acquired by a female Hindu before the Act, her limited interest will become full interest provided that (a) the property was possessed by her on the date of commencement of the Act and (b) the property was possessed by her as a limited owner. If the female Hindu was not in possession of the limited estate on the date of the Act, the interest of the female Hindu will not enlarge into an absolute estate. In the absence of any possession of any property acquired by the female Hindu prior to the Act, there is no estate to be enlarged into a full one.

Property acquired after the Act

On and from the date of commencement of the Hindu Succession Act, the concept of Hindu Widow's estate with limited power stands annulled and abrogated. In *Jagannatha Pillai v. Kunjithapatham Pillai*¹⁹, it was observed that the legal effect of Section 14(1) would be that after the coming into operation of the Act, there would be no property in respect of which it could be contended by anyone that the Hindu female is only a limited owner and not a full owner.

C. RIGHT TO DISPOSE OF PROPERTY BY WILL

Section 30 of the principal Act has been amended by inclusion of a female Hindu, thus recognizing her right of disposal of property and empowering her with the right to dispose of any property by will or other testamentary disposition.

Section 30 provides:²⁰

Testamentary succession.- Any Hindu may dispose of by will or other testamentary disposition any property, which is capable of being so disposed of by him or by her, in accordance with the provisions of the Indian Succession Act, 1925, or any other law for the time being in force and applicable to Hindus.

¹⁹ *Jagannatha Pillai v. Kunjithapatham Pillai*, AIR 1987 SC 1493.

²⁰ Section 30, The Hindu Succession Act, 1956.

Prior to this Act, neither under Mitakshara nor under Dayabhaga law, could a widow or other limited heir in any case dispose of by will any property inherited by her or any portion thereof, irrespective of whether the property was movable or immovable. But, as under section 14 she is a full owner of all property howsoever acquired and held by her, she can dispose it off by will or other testamentary disposition. An owner of property normally has a right of disposition over his property; inclusive of the right to devise or bequeath such property. This section reiterates and reaffirms such right.²¹

IV. A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF INHERITANCE RIGHTS OF WOMEN UNDER THE HINDU SUCCESSION ACT, 1956 AND SANTHAL CUSTOMARY LAWS

The inheritance rights of women as provided under the Hindu Succession Act, 1956 and under the Santhal customary laws have been discussed at length in the above Parts. The differences between the two are inevitably noticeable and a comparative study of the inheritance rights of women under the two is only desirable. This comparative study is done under the following heads:

A. RIGHT OF WOMEN OVER PROPERTY

Under the Hindu Succession Act, 1956 as amended by the Hindu Succession (Amendment) Act, 2005, hereinafter referred to as Act of 1956, Section 6 provides that a daughter of a coparcener in a joint Hindu family governed by the Mitakshara law becomes a coparcener in her own right from her birth and thus enjoys rights equal to those enjoyed by a son of a coparcener. She is invested with all the rights including the right to seek partition of the coparcenary property and to become Karta of the joint Hindu family.

It further stipulates that any property to which a female Hindu becomes entitled as a coparcener would be held by her with all the incidents, rights and liabilities of coparcenary ownership and would be construed as property being capable of being disposed of by such female by testamentary disposition. The wife of a deceased coparcener is also entitled to a share as his widow.

On the other hand, under Santhal customary laws, the daughter ordinarily has no right at all in the property. Land is usually equally divided among the brothers, with certain small portions going to daughters as dowry. She cannot ask for partition as a matter of right and in the event of her brothers separating, some land may be kept by her father or brothers for financing

²¹Desai, *supra* note 16, at 486.

her marriage and maintaining her. It must be noted that that is done only to fulfill their duties towards her and does not confer upon her any rights as such. On partition of her father's property, she has no right to any share in it and only has a right to maintenance. If her father or her brothers or her father's agnates are not willing to discharge their duties, she can claim enough land for her sustenance till marriage. In certain cases, unmarried girls may inherit land, but their land reverts to their brothers on their marriage.

If a woman is left a widow without any sons, it is her husband's father or brothers who will inherit the whole property. She will only get one *bandi* of paddy, one calf, one *bati* and one cloth, and will have to go back to her parents' house. If a widow has daughters, their paternal grandfather and uncles will take charge of mother and daughters, and possession over the property. When the daughters come of age, they will marry off the daughters and they will also give the daughters whatever presents their father would have given them at their marriage. After all the daughters are married, the widow will be given the perquisites of a childless widow and will have to go to live in either her father's house or with her daughters. The widow with a son will keep all the property in her own possession; the grandfather and uncles can only properly look on to see that the wife does not waste the property. If a widow remarries before her sons get married, their paternal grandfather and uncles take possession of the property and she ceases to have any right to get anything. At times, she is given a calf out of kindness which is called *bhandkar*.²²

B. RIGHT TO FULL OWNERSHIP OF PROPERTY

Section 14 of the Act of 1956 converted the limited ownership of a female Hindu into full-fledged ownership including a power to dispose it off at her pleasure. For widows who, on the date of the passing of the Act, were in possession of the property as limited owners, it was provided that henceforth, they would hold these as full owners thereof.

Section 14 provides that any property possessed by a female Hindu, whether acquired before or after the commencement of this Act, shall be held by her as full owner thereof and not as a limited owner. 'Property' includes both movable and immovable property acquired by a female Hindu by inheritance or devise, or at a partition or in lieu of maintenance or arrears of maintenance or by gift from any person, whether a relative or not, before, at or after her marriage, or by her own skill or exertion, or by purchase or by prescription or in any other manner whatsoever and also any such property held by her as *stridhana* immediately before the commencement of this Act.

²²Sahu, *supra* note 9, at 76.

On the other hand, under Santhal customary laws, with regard to the right of the widow, her position is that of a Hindu widow²³ having right to maintenance only. If her husband died while he was joint holder with his brothers, she will continue to live in the family and her position will not differ materially from what it was in her husband's lifetime. Her right to maintenance shall continue and if her husband's family neglects her without reasonable cause, she can demand land sufficient for her sustenance. If there is a partition in the entire family, the widow and her children will get the share which would have gone to her husband had he been alive; however, she only gets life estate like Hindu widow's estate²⁴.

C. RIGHT OF DISPOSAL OF PROPERTY

Section 30 of the Act of 1956 provides a female Hindu with the right of disposal of property and empowers her with the right to dispose of any property by will or other testamentary disposition.

On the other hand, under Santhal customary laws as a woman ordinarily does not have a right over property and whenever has it viz. as a daughter or widow, it is a limited estate over which she only enjoys the right to maintenance and not the right of disposal.

As seen above, this comparative study reveals the fact that women are at a disadvantageous position in respect of inheritance rights under the Santhal customary laws as compared to the Hindu Succession Act, 1956.

V. APPLICABILITY OF THE HINDU SUCCESSION ACT, 1956 TO SANTHALS

Many persons belonging to aboriginal tribes have been absorbed into the Hindu faith and come to be governed by Hindu law. It seems to be accepted that Hindu law applies to tribal people whose way of life, habits and culture have been influenced by Hindus, and who profess Hinduism.²⁵

The court held that although it had not been established that the Santhals of Manbhum had been converted to Hinduism as the Santhals had still retained some of their old relics and thus they had not become completely Hinduised; all these grounds are not sufficient to hold that the parties not governed by the Hindu Law in matters of inheritance and succession. It is not essential for them to be completely Hinduised, it is enough if they have

²³ Her status is that of a Hindu widow as before the coming into force of the Hindu Succession Act, 1956.

²⁴ Roy, *supra* note 13, at 369- 370.

²⁵ *Dhanurjaya Kirsani v. SukraKirsani and ors.*, AIR 1987 Ori 205.

been sufficiently Hinduised so as to be governed by the Hindu Law in matters of inheritance and succession.²⁶

In *Narendra Narain v. Nagendra Narain*²⁷, the tests to be applied for the determination of the question whether a non-Hindu-tribe has been so 'Hinduised' have been pointed out. It has been held that adoption of Hindu names, performance of pujas, such as Durga Puja, Kali Puja, etc., employment of priests, offering of pindas, observance of a period of mourning in the event of death, performance of funeral ceremonies were sufficient proof that a family has adopted Hindu religion. The test consists in their acknowledging themselves to be Hindus and in adopting social usages, the retention of a few traits of their ante-Hinduism period is, however, accepted. In *Ramayya v. Josephine Elizabeth*²⁸, it was held that a formal conversion is not required for a person to become a Hindu.

The term 'Hindu' is used in a theological sense as distinguished from national or racial sense, and consequently, many persons belonging to aboriginal tribes and origins have been absorbed in the Hindu faith and come to be governed by Hindu law, for example, Naiks in Madhya Pradesh who were originally of Gond origin. It was held that the Santhals of village Kutchai share Hindu beliefs, observe Hindu usages and practices, worship Hindu deities and their mode of life is that of Hindu and consequently they have become sufficiently Hinduised and hence, are governed by the Hindu law in the matter of succession and inheritance.²⁹

In *Krittibash Mahton v. Budhan Mahtani*³⁰, it was stated that in cases relating to inheritance among aboriginals it is necessary to enquire that even if Hinduised (slightly partially, or completely), whether they have abandoned the tribal custom as to inheritance and if they have abandoned the tribal custom, which particular school of Hindu Law have they adhered to.

Hence, the well-established position in law is that it is possible that aboriginals of non-Hindu origin can become sufficiently Hinduised so that in the matter of inheritance and succession they are governed by the Hindu Law, except if any variant custom to such law is proved.³¹ In case it is established that the parties of non-Hindu origin have been Hinduised, they

²⁶*Budhu Majhi & Anr. v. Dukhan Majhi & Ors.*, AIR 1956 Pat 123 [*"BudhuMajhi*, AIR 1971 Pat 185"].

²⁷*Narendra Narain v. Nagendra Narain*, AIR 1929 Cal 577.

²⁸*Ramayya v. Josephine Elizabeth*, AIR 1937 Mad 172.

²⁹*Langa Manjhi & Ors. v. Jaba Majhian & Ors.*, AIR 1971 Pat 185 [*"LangaManjhi*, AIR 1971 Pat 185"].

³⁰*Krittibash Mahton v. Budhan Mahtani*, AIR 1925 Pat 733.

³¹*Chunku Manjhi v. Bhabani Majhan*, AIR 1946 Pat 218.

are governed by the rules of Hindu Law and the burden of proving that the old custom of that community exists lies upon the party who claims so.³²

VI. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Women empowerment and gender justice are common phenomena of the modern democratic world, which is receiving a high degree of popularity in all the societies, but nevertheless, it must be implemented keeping in view social concerns and with the help and support of each and every component of society.³³ Empowerment of women, leading to an equal social status in society depends, inter alia, on their right to hold and inherit property. Several legal reforms have been introduced, yet equal status remains elusive.

The public policy and constitutional philosophy envisaged under Articles 38, 39, 46 and 15(1) and (3) and 14 is to accord social and economic democracy to women as assured in the Preamble of the Constitution. In other words, they frown upon gender discrimination and aim at elimination of obstacles to enjoy political, economic, social and cultural rights on equal terms. The utility of law depends on its vitality and ability to serve as sustaining pillar of society. In an evolving society, the contours of law must constantly keep changing as civilization and culture advances. Customs and mores must undergo change with the advent of time.³⁴

Women have always been discriminated against and have suffered and are suffering discrimination in silence. They have been subjected to all inequity, inequality, indignity, and discrimination. Articles 13, 14, 15, 16 of the Constitution of India and other related articles prohibit discrimination on the ground of sex. It is mandatory, therefore, to render them socio-economic justice so as to ensure their dignity of person, so that they are brought into the mainstream of the national life.

Scheduled Tribes were not brought within the fold of definition of Hindus to protect their customs and identity.³⁵ In *Gazula Dasaratha Rama Rao v. State of Andhra Pradesh*,³⁶ the Supreme Court expressed the view that Article 13(1) which says that laws in force in India before the commencement of the Constitution shall be void if inconsistent with Fundamental Rights “includes custom or usage having the force of law”. The Court observed that

³²*Langa Manjhi*, AIR 1971 Pat 185.

³³ R.K. Mishra, *Hindu Jurisprudence on Succession and Gender Equality: A Critical Study*, 1(1) THE LEGAL ANALYST 42, 48 (2011).

³⁴ *Madhu Kishwar & others v. State of Bihar & others*, AIR 1996 SC 1864 [“*MadhuKishwar*, AIR 1996 SC 1864”].

³⁵*Id.*

³⁶*Gazula Dasaratha Rama Rao v. State of Andhra Pradesh*, AIR 1961 SC 564.

even if a custom has been recognized by law, that custom has to yield to a Fundamental Right.³⁷

In *Madhu Kishwarv. State of Bihar*³⁸, Ramaswami, J. expressed the view that customs of tribals, though elevated to the status of law by Article 13(1) (a), yet it is essential that the customs inconsistent with or repugnant to constitutional Scheme must always yield place to fundamental rights. The majority generally agreed with this approach though it adopted a conservative approach to the specific situation and desisted from declaring a tribal custom as inconsistent with Article 14 saying that to do so would bring about a chaos in the existing state of law.³⁹

On the basis of the entire study, there is no denying the fact that Santhal women are indeed at a very disadvantageous position with regard to inheritance rights as provided to them under the Santhal customary laws. The provisions of the Santhal customary laws regarding inheritance rights of women are indeed against all norms of equality and justice. Further, provisions under the Hindu Succession Act, 1956 accord equal rights to women and as is evident from several judicial decisions it can be made applicable on the Santhals professing the Hindu religion which will result in the enjoyment of equal inheritance rights by Santhal women.

Keeping in view the factual position of the Santhal customary laws and the provisions under the Hindu Succession Act, 1956 with regard to the inheritance rights of women, in order to alter this unfortunate status of Santhal women, the researcher humbly advances the following suggestions:

- The Santhal elders, leaders and the legislature should get together and devise means to provide equal inheritance rights to women.
- That changes be introduced in the Santhal customary law, so that equal inheritance rights are afforded to women; and
- For those Santhals who have adopted the Hindu religion, provisions relating to inheritance of property by women be made applicable on them in the light of the fact that the judiciary has already held the Santhals in certain localities to have been sufficiently Hinduised and made Hindu inheritance laws applicable on them.

³⁷M.P. Jain, Indian Constitutional Law 847, Wadhwa & Co. Nagpur (2009).

³⁸*Madhu Kishwar*, AIR 1996 SC 1864.

³⁹*Madhu Kishwar*, AIR 1996 SC 1864 at 1885.